

ISic1169

I.Sicily inscription 1169

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

(grey)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 683

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀττικῶν
2. Ἀγαθίνου
3. χάριε

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644944

EDCS 64900777

Bibliography

Brugnone, A. 1974. Iscrizione greche del museo civico di Termini Imerese.

Kokalos. 20: 218-264. At 8

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1971. Tre epitafi inediti. *Kokalos*. 17: 184-186. At 186 no.2
tav.55.2

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1169. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351687>